

Reclaiming the resources we make

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DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845098>

Abstract

As educational designers, we dedicate countless hours to creating resources, tipsheets, and digital assets with the intent of building capability in our institutions. Yet, the moment we step away from that institution, our ideas and everything we've created are left behind. Frustrated by this disconnect, I developed a process for converting, revising, updating and building on these resources into a space that is mine. This paper unpacks the motivations and methods behind the creation of my blog, [The Educational Designer](#). It details a refusal to let institutional norms define my professional voice, which led to a liberated approach to evolving my practice on my own terms. I invite others to use this work as a starting point to reimagine their experience, skills, and identity as distinctly individual and valuable.

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Third space challenges

The position occupied by educational designers, often referred to as the third space, encompasses peripheral yet vital roles in educational development. This space is frequently characterised by several challenges that directly inform our motivations and actions. Among these are:

The challenges of third spaces

- Lack of recognition
- Instability
- Feeling like a cog in a wheel
- Lack of agency
- Lack of voice

Lack of professional recognition

Educational designers regularly support academics in the ideation and implementation of new initiatives, contributing to the elevation of educational standards. However, their contributions remain largely unacknowledged in subsequent awards, publications or presentations by academic staff.

Workforce instability

Despite repeatedly being described in leadership discussions as “essential”, designers are often offered short-term contracts and limited tenure, with roles adjunct to the lifecycle of projects or initiatives and their perceived completion.

Putting out fires

Tenured staff often experience persistent workload demand, reacting to institutional changes such as the shift to remote teaching, alterations in assessment practices, or the adoption of generative AI tools. This often occurs without recognition of our achievements or time to pause, reflect, and evaluate, before the next initiative has been dictated.

Limited agency and voice

Institutional change invariably occurs with little or superficial consultation, and educational designers are often engaged as facilitators of the new initiative, policy or technology, regardless of their professional perspectives. Advocacy for quality education may be stifled by authoritative leadership and rushed initiatives, with voices frequently overlooked.

Reflection and Motivations

In 2023, with ten years of experience as an educational designer, I recognised a need to assert greater agency over my professional outputs. In consideration of the issues above, my goals emerged:

Reflecting on 10 years of educational design

- I needed to:
- showcase my skills
 - retain my own IP
 - establish my own voice

Showcasing capabilities

I sought to establish a public platform that would provide tangible evidence of my skills and expertise. This needed to be separated from my workplace to establish my individual identity.

What is your voice?

Your voice is the freedom to be able to express yourself in a way that is uniquely you, with all your diverse perspectives, representing all your skills, experience and knowledge.

Retaining intellectual property

While institutions retain legal ownership of the published resources we have produced, the underlying concepts and ideas remain ours. Redeveloping these ideas into new formats allowed me to retain ownership over my ideas.

Establishing an independent professional voice

Institutional writing conventions, such as the “Monash tone of voice”, restrict authentic expression. I required a platform where nuance, critique, and personal identity could be freely expressed, distinct from institutional constraints. I needed a way to be able to say, “I’m living in an episode of Utopia, and I’m a little bit dead inside”. This is not the Monash tone of voice.

So, what did I do?

Showcase my skills Retain my own IP Establish my own voice

“The Educational Designer”

Defining professional voice

Professional voice in this context extends beyond the functional content of communications. It represents the synthesis of experience, knowledge, identity, and communicative autonomy. Although institutions may support diverse perspectives, formal etiquette and tone requirements limit such freedom. My process focused on articulating my educational philosophy in a manner representative of my distinct identity.

Strategies for redeveloping resources

In the interest of bringing others along on the journey, I am sharing the various strategies that I have used to redevelop my work. This section presents practical strategies for reclaiming your work, extending its reach, and expressing your unique professional voice more fully.

1. Use Generative AI to revise resources

Expanding on ideas

If you have “quick tips” resources, give these ideas to AI to see how it expands on the topic.

Prompt: You are an education expert writing a blog post on [topic]. Elaborate on these ideas, explain why they are important, and give examples. Here are the ideas: [1], [2], [3].

Rewriting text

Generative AI makes deliberate attempts to create a homogenous voice, which is in opposition to my intention to establish my unique voice. If the original writing is already well-formed, this helps retain the ideas and change the phrasing.

Prompt: Rewrite the following text, changing the sentence structure, word choice, and overall flow while preserving the core meaning and key information. Aim for a version that is noticeably different from the original in terms of phrasing and organisation but conveys the same essential ideas. Here is the text [text].

New ideas

If you’re working on something new, write your ideas down first, then review the literature, and then prompt AI. This helps to have more confidence in your own work. This means that AI can help make the process more comprehensive, rather than outsourcing the critical components to AI.

Prompts:

I’m working on a blog post on [topic]. Can you find any gaps in research or unique angles?

I’m working on a blog post on [topic]. Can you suggest some potential questions people may want answered on this topic?

I have an idea for a blog post on [topic] but haven’t formed it well. Ask me questions to help me form my ideas more clearly. Here is my idea: [idea].

2. Find old, outdated, or no longer used resources

Outdated or archived resources can be revisited and updated in light of contemporary educational innovations (I’m looking at you, Generative AI). This can give you an opportunity to review the concept, ensuring it is in line with the current literature. This strategy can be difficult without a

How did I do it?

- Developed strategies.
- Added some shiny new ideas.

What strategies did I use to redevelop the resources?

1. Use AI to rewrite my resources
2. Find old, outdated, or no longer used resources
3. Change the format
4. Change the examples
5. Use voice to text
6. Track everything
7. Write in my own time

great filing system, but go back through old projects and initiatives and find whatever resources you created that were of an advisory or informative nature. Don't forget the shared/group folders and your personal folders (obviously, only searching for the resources you developed yourself).

3. *Change the format*

When redeveloping something currently in use, change the format to ensure it's sufficiently different from the original. Here are some formats I commonly use:

Commonly asked questions from educators with a response, reasoning and advice.

- Example: Student norms: Why can't they just do it the way I want them to?

Strategies for a [common topic] I'm asked for support with.

- Example: How to improve group work processes for equitable, engaging, and productive student collaboration

Two/three strategies for [topic].

- Example: Two long-term strategies to create inclusive learning environments

[Verbing] [topic] with steps and advice.

- Example: Step-by-step: Building impactful branching scenarios

Simplifying [topic] by using less institutional jargon

- Example: Demystifying learning outcomes: What they are and how to write them

4. *Change the examples*

Rather than limit examples to your primary disciplinary context, give AI your discipline-specific example and ask AI to create an equivalent example in another discipline. AI will provide a broad example, and you'll need to add specificity. Get in touch with other third spacers, ask them what they might use in their disciplines. This broadens the scope and applicability of the redeveloped resources and serves as a way of expanding your knowledge, experience, and connection base.

5. *Use voice to text*

 Voice typing When there is significant commonality in advice given during consultations, I capture this via voice-to-text tools during routine activities, providing both new ideas for blog posts and a feedback database. You can use voice typing on Google Docs, or use the "mic" button on your keyboard when you're on your phone. Have a cloud-based notebook or document system on the go, and take a few minutes after each meeting to verbalise the advice you've just given. If you can remember in the moment, turn it on during Zoom meetings when you're speaking to capture the advice you give. Just make sure you're only capturing your words, not the words of others.

6. *Track everything*

Use a systematic, procedural approach and capture the redevelopment in a spreadsheet to prevent redundancy across posts and resources. Capturing this in a spreadsheet ensures a more

comprehensive coverage, including links to the existing content, new content, and notes on what parts have been captured.

7. *Write in your own time*

Perhaps most importantly, this work must be conducted outside of work hours. This ensures there is no conflict of interest and the IP remains your own. This strategy pairs well with voice typing and your phone's virtual assistant (Siri, etc). Often the best ideas come while driving, walking or doing chores. Verbalising the idea means they don't get lost and you don't have to stop and write anything down because you can speak it to capture it (caveat: obviously, pay attention while driving).

Outcomes and significance

This approach gave me several outcomes addressing the challenges outlined above. The content published on my blog remains my IP, offering personal recognition for years of development of knowledge, skills and experience as an educational designer. The independent authorship gives me agency, enabling freedom in topic selection and promoting exploration over reactive, institution-driven content production. The blog facilitates my authentic voice, identity, and self-expression, which allows the integration of wit, personality, and critique in my writing. This, in turn, enables me to showcase my distinct professional identity.

What did this give me?

- Personal recognition
- Agency
- Voice

Reflection

The purpose of sharing this process was to encourage fellow educational designers to assert ownership of their skills, knowledge, and identity. As part of my presentation, I included a call to action for their third space professionals to reclaim their resources and share their journey. A similar journey is that of my fellow colleague, EDI advocate and educational designer, Aster Cosmos, whose blog represents their own passions, skills, knowledge and experience, exemplified in [one of their posts about the Third Space Symposium](#). “You were so right about using time between things to do material building for your brand. Ranting into my phone in speech-to-text mode while I'm driving home is an excellent way to make blog posts!”

Initially, I expressed limited interest in actively promoting the blog, citing constraints of time and energy. However, in recent months, I have found renewed motivation to engage with strategies related to search engine optimisation (SEO) and digital dissemination. I have learnt that visibility in search engine results actually requires verification with platforms like Google search to ensure a website's presence is recognised and accessible to a broader audience. So I'm currently in the process of tweaking my blog posts in line with SEO strategies, but it's a slow process.

A call to action

In the presentation, I also wanted others to feel the same sense of empowerment I've felt from writing in my own voice and owning my own words. I wanted to see other people reclaiming their

professional identities and resources. I still want this, so if you're reading this and it strikes a chord: Start the journey, keep in touch, and send me a link to your blog, because I'd love to subscribe.

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Why am I talking about it here and now?

